

Support for Making a Metadata Collection for Research Data Visible

Background and Need

As part of the CARDS project (Collaboratively Advancing Research Data Support, <https://www.bihealth.org/de/aktuell/cards>), the Cluster of Excellence Science of Intelligence was supported in the further development of its existing metadata collection for research datasets. The main question was how already collected information on datasets could be made publicly visible with as little additional effort as possible and better integrated into the existing communication and publication structures of the cluster.

The starting point was a Google Docs structure that was already used in the cluster for collecting different types of research-related information. This included publications, research datasets, activities, awards and further outputs. At the beginning, the collection of research datasets contained around 50 entries. For publications, a technical workflow already existed: the metadata entered in Google Docs was exported via a Python script, converted into a BibTeX format and then integrated into the website of the cluster.

For the research datasets, a comparable publication workflow had not yet been implemented. The datasets were documented internally, but they were not publicly shown on the website. At the same time, it became clear that building a separate data platform would not be realistic under the given conditions. Such a platform had originally been planned in the context of a possible follow-up funding, but was no longer pursued after the cluster funding ended.

The need was therefore a pragmatic extension of the existing structures. The existing collection should be further developed in such a way that research datasets become more visible, without creating new places for data entry or additional maintenance effort for the cluster team.

Solution and Implementation

In a joint meeting with the Research Data Committee of the cluster, the existing table structure, the technical workflow and possible improvements were reviewed. Typical limitations of a table-based metadata collection became visible, especially inconsistent field contents, limited possibilities for categorisation and the missing technical connection to the public presentation of research outputs.

As a first improvement, it was suggested to add a keyword field to the existing table. This field should enable a simple thematic classification of the datasets and may later support filtering as well as their presentation on project pages. Instead of introducing a comprehensive metadata schema, a limited adjustment was chosen, which increases the value of the existing collection without substantially increasing the maintenance effort.

In parallel, the existing publication workflow was reused for research datasets. Since a Python script already existed that exported publication data from Google Docs and

converted it into BibTeX, this technical structure could be extended for metadata on datasets. After approval by the Research Data Committee, access to the corresponding Git repository was provided to the Data Steward and the existing script was adapted by the Data Steward so that research datasets could also be read from the Google document and prepared for the website workflow.

The adaptations were versioned in Git and returned to the committee for review. After positive feedback, further implementation steps were carried out by the responsible members of the cluster. These included cleaning the table contents, smaller adjustments to the field logic and the technical integration of the dataset entries into WordPress.

Application and Outlook

As a result, the research datasets and research software of the cluster are now publicly shown on the website of Science of Intelligence:

<https://www.scienceofintelligence.de/research/data/>

The entries are therefore no longer documented only in an internal working table, but are visible as own research outputs on the website of the cluster. Due to the website developer's limited capacity, however, only a minimal presentation could initially be implemented. Mainly basic bibliographic information is visible, such as authors, year, title and in some cases the indication as dataset or software. A more detailed metadata description, for example with abstract, license information, persistent identifiers, repository links, access conditions, file formats or project relations, was not yet systematically implemented in this step.

The most important direct added value is the improved visibility and recognition of research data and software as independent scientific contributions. The public presentation makes visible that, in addition to classical publications, datasets, code and software are also produced in the cluster, which are relevant for transparency, traceability and potential reuse. This strengthens the connection to Open Science practices and supports a broader view on scientific achievements. In this way, the measure also relates to CoARA principles, according to which scientific contributions should be made visible and recognized more broadly than only through classical publication-based indicators.

The solution should be understood as a pragmatic first step to create visibility and recognition for already documented data-related results.